

Table S1: Correlations between SVR, Oxygen pressure and CPET data

		Oxygen Pressure	VO ₂ /kg peak	Cardiac Output peak	Stroke volume peak	Oxygen Pulse peak	CR	Cardio vascular Efficiency (VO ₂ /Work slope)	Ventilatory Efficiency (VE/VCO ₂ slope)	Oxygen uptake Extraction Slope (OUES)	SBP peak	MAP peak	DBP peak
Systemic vascular resistance peak	r	0,883	-0,711	-0,689	-0,627	-0,633	-0,232	-0,378	0,325	-0,647	0,041	0,105	0,141
	p	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	0,167	<0,001	<0,001
		Systemic vascular resistance	VO ₂ /kg peak	Cardiac Output peak	Stroke volume peak	Oxygen Pulse peak	CR	Cardio vascular Efficiency (VO ₂ /Work slope)	Ventilatory Efficiency (VE/VCO ₂ slope)	Oxygen uptake Extraction Slope (OUES)	SBP peak	MAP peak	DBP peak
Oxygen Pressure	r	0,883	-0,792	-0,786	-0,671	-0,732	-0,241	-0,465	0,347	-0,730	-0,027	0,052	0,119
	p	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	0,367	0,083	<0,001

Legend; CR, Chronotropic response; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; MAP, mean arterial pressure.